
ASSESSMENT OF PREVALENT DIETARY PATTERN AMONG PROSTATE CANCER PATIENTS IN ONDO CITY, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Understanding the prevalent dietary patterns and their implications for prostate cancer is crucial for informing targeted public health interventions and dietary guidelines.

Objectives: This study investigated the dietary patterns influencing prostate cancer in Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among men aged 30 years and above, diagnosed with prostate cancer at the University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital. Ethical approval was obtained from the UNIMEDTHC Review Committee (Protocol No. UNIMED/024/ERC/150). Data were collected using structured questionnaires, 24-hour dietary recalls, and food frequency questionnaires. Analysis was performed with IBM SPSS version 27.0 to evaluate dietary patterns and lifestyle practices.

Results: The findings revealed high consumption of carbohydrate staples such as rice (30.1%) and cassava-based products including “fufu” (21.9%), with moderate protein intake primarily from red meat (27.4%) and beans (21.9%). Daily fruit and vegetable intake were reported by 49.3% of respondents, while physical inactivity (58.9%) and alcohol consumption (60.3%) were common lifestyle factors. Additionally, 69.9% reported relief from symptoms after drinking cold water while 49.3% experienced relief from warm water. Pearson correlation showed a significant relationship between dietary habits and prostate cancer ($p = 0.038$) leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Conclusion: The study highlights a strong association between dietary patterns and prostate cancer. Public health strategies should therefore promote balanced diets, create awareness of dietary risks, and encourage healthy lifestyle practices to reduce the burden of prostate cancer.

Keywords: Prostate Cancer, Dietary Patterns, Nutrition, Lifestyle, Public Health

INTRODUCTION

Prostate cancer is a type of cancer that grows in the prostate gland which is a small round gland found below a man’s bladder (CDC, 2023). The prostate gland produces seminal fluid that maintains and transports sperm (AskMayoExpert, 2022). Prostate cancer in most cases begins when cells in the prostate gland mutate and start to grow uncontrollably forming a tumor (AskMayoExpert, 2022).

Prostate cancer is the second most prevalent form of cancer, the fifth cause of cancer-related death among men worldwide (Bray, et al., 2018). In Ni-

geria, it is the leading cause of cancer deaths in men (Akor, 2023) with an estimated 51,000 new cases annually (GLOBACON, 2021). The incidence of clinical prostate cancer rate in Nigeria may be as high as that observed in black men in the United States, indicating a possible common genetic predisposition (WCRFI, 2023).

The likelihood of receiving a cancer diagnosis is higher in developing countries such as Nigeria and this has been linked to insufficient health education, lack of awareness, poverty, the absence of prostate cancer screening, sub-standard healthcare

facilities, and unhealthy diet (Owolabi et. al., 2023).

In 2020, there were 15,306 new cases of prostate cancer and 8,517 deaths from the disease in Nigeria (Akor, 2023). Previous studies have unveiled that the occurrence of prostate cancer in Nigerian Healthcare institutions was documented at 127,100 cases, suggesting a national risk of prostate cancer at 2% with a total of 110,000 cases. The death rate was reported to be 20,000 annually (Osegbe, (n.d)).

Assertions from the literature imply that a person's knowledge of prostate cancer is related to their age, income, education, positive family history, and accessibility to care (Owolabi et. al., 2023). Further research might be required to fully understand the complexities of the genetic factor, environmental factor, and socio-economic factor and their contribution to the disparity in prostate cancer risk (Adeyinka, 2023).

Diet and lifestyle factors have been identified as major modifiable risk factors influencing prostate cancer development. According to (Michal et. al., 2021), Diet plays a crucial role in maintaining optimal prostate health, the consumption of nutrients such as saturated and trans-fatty acids can cause disruptions in prostate hormonal regulation, oxidative stress, inflammation, alters signaling for cell growth, and lipid metabolism.

Over time, several studies has shown that specific dietary habits may either increase or decrease the risk of developing prostate cancer (WCRFI, 2018).

The impact of nutrients and dietary habits on the occurrence of prostate cancer in Nigeria is a modifiable risk factor and an important (Michal et. al., 2021) and very controversial subject, with some suggestions indicating that high consumption of certain foods, such as processed meats, red meat, and dairy products, may increase the risk (IARC, 2022). However, evidence suggests consumption of a diet rich in vegetables (such as tomatoes, which contain lycopene that is associated with a lower risk of prostate cancer), fruits, fish, whole grain and legumes (American Cancer Society, 2022), as well as nutrients like proteins, fats, carbohydrates, flavonoids, stilbenes, lycopene, polyphenols, selenium, vitamins (A, D, and E), calcium and alpha-linoleic acid that can contribute to the prevention of prostate cancer development (Niçlis et. al., 2022). A balanced diet, which includes a variety of essential nutrients from all food groups plays a crucial role in maintaining health (WHO, 2022). By adopting a healthy diet and reducing intakes of these harmful nutrients, growth factor signaling and lipid metabolism can be supported thereby mitigating the risk of prostate cancer (Michal et. al., 2021).

Ondo city, Ondo state, provides a unique demographic and dietary profile that may influence prostate cancer prevalence. The dietary habits of its inhabitants are influenced by cultural practices, local food availability and socio-economic factors. However, there is a lack of comprehensive studies inves-

tigating the prevalence dietary patterns and their impact on prostate cancer within this specific region. Understanding these prevalent dietary patterns and their implications for prostate cancer in this context is crucial for informing targeted public health interventions and dietary guidelines.

Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Ondo city, a prominent urban center in Ondo state, southwestern Nigeria. The city lies between latitudes 7°6'0" N and longitudes 4°50'24" E, and stands at an elevation of approximately 287 meter (940 feet) and serve as a vital junction connecting Ife, Akure and Okitipupa (Encyclopedia Britannica, (2022)).

The survey was conducted at the University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital (UNIMEDTHC), Ondo city, Ondo state. This hospital serves as a referral hospital to all the general and private hospitals in Ondo state and neighboring states which include Kogi, Ekiti, and Edo states. Services rendered here are 24 hours.

2.2 Study Design and Duration.

An observational cross-sectional study design was carried out in UNIMEDTHC to identify the prevalence of dietary patterns influencing prostate cancer among men in Ondo city.

The study lasted approximately 6 months following ethical approval.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula for finite populations.

Questionnaire Validation and Pre-Testing

A semi-structured questionnaire was designed based on validated dietary and lifestyle assessment tools. It underwent review by a Public Health Practitioner and a Nutrition specialist expert for content validity and was pre-tested among 10 respondents in a facility outside the local government to ensure clarity, reliability, and cultural appropriateness.

Data Collection

Data was collected through Self-administered questionnaires, including sections on socio-demographic information (age, education level, and marital status), dietary habits, family history, lifestyle factors (smoking status, physical activity, and sedentary lifestyle). Additionally, food frequency and 24-hour dietary recall were used to assess dietary patterns. Purposive sampling method was used to select participants who are residents of Ondo city and had been diagnosed with prostate cancer, to ensure a diverse and unbiased representation of the

The study's purpose, risk and benefits of research were explained to participants to help them better understand before giving informed consent and further ethical procedures were followed in addition to obtaining written and informed consent.

2.3 Data Analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted using the SPSS epidemiological software package (version 27.0). Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and dietary variables. Pearson correlation was used to examine the relationship between dietary habits and prostate cancer.

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Demographic Information

Variables		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	Under 30 years	8	11.4
	30-50	18	25.7
	Over 50	47	64.4
Marital status	Single	19	27.2
	Married	25	34.2
	Divorced	16	22.8
	Widowed	13	18.6
Education level	No education	9	12.9
	Primary education	13	18.6
	Secondary education	19	27.1
	Tertiary Education	32	43.8

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents (64.4%) were men over 50 years of age, this reflects the age group most vulnerable to prostate cancer. Most had attained tertiary education (43.8%), which may increase health awareness and healthcare seeking behavior. This aligns with global and local evidence that prostate cancer predominantly affects older men and that higher education may improve awareness (Owolabi et. al., 2023).

Table 2 show a strong reliance on starchy staples such as rice (30.1%) and cassava-based products like fufu (21.9%). Red meat (27.4%) and beans (21.9%) were the most common serving of protein source. The low diversity of fruits and vegetable consumed does not reflect limited availability but rather low frequency of consumption across most fruit and vegetable types. For instance, only 1.4% consumed avocado pawpaw, and fewer than 10% regularly ate many of the listed options. This pattern

Table 2: Dietary Pattern and Lifestyle factor

VARIABLES		FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Carbohydrate	Yam	10	13.7
	Cornmeal (Akamu/Ogi)	11	15.1
	Rice	22	30.1
	Eba	14	19.2
	Fufu/Akpu (made from cassava)	16	21.9
Protein	Beans	16	21.9
	Red meat	20	27.4
	Egg	17	23.3
	Milk	10	13.7
Fruits	Mangoes	11	15.1
	Apples	7	9.6
	Walnut	2	2.7
	Oranges	6	8.2
	Plantain	3	4.1
	Coconut	4	5.5
	Avocado	1	1.4
	African cherries	2	2.7
	Palm fruit	1	1.4
	Water melon	8	11
	Guavas	8	11
Vegetables	Bananas	8	11
	Pineapple	6	8.2
	Cashew	2	2.7
	Pawpaw	1	1.4
	Grapes	2	2.7
	Tomato	9	12.3
	Onions	17	23.3
	Cabbage	0	0.0
	Carrots	4	5.5
	Sweet potatoes	5	7.1
	Cucumbers	4	5.5
Pepper	1	1.4	
Okra	4	5.5	
Spinach (Efo)	5	7.1	
Cocoyam	5	7.1	
Cassava	3	4.1	
Yam	8	11	
Bitter leaf	5	7.1	
Ugwu	3	4.1	
Alcohol	Palm wine	30	41.1
	Beer	16	21.9
	Local gin	12	16.4
	Wine	15	20.5
Beverages	Water	25	34.2
	Soft drinks	15	20.5
	Tea	17	23.3
	Coffee	9	12.3
Supplements	Vitamin D	23	31.5
	Fish oil	21	28.8
	Selenium	8	11
	Zinc	10	13.7
	Saw palmetto	0	0.0
	Iron	8	11
	Magnesium	3	4.1
Cold Water	Yes	51	69.9
	No	22	30.1
Warm Water	Yes	36	49.3
	No	37	50.7

indicates that despite access to a range of produce, daily intake is concentrated on a narrow selection, reducing exposure to protective antioxidants (such as lycopene and flavonoids) and phytochemicals. The high prevalence of alcohol consumption,

especially palm wine (41.1%), and physical inactivity (58.9%) further increases the risk of prostate cancer. The findings reflect the nutrition transition in urban Nigeria, where traditional plant-based diets are being replaced with calorie-dense and nutrient-poor foods. Such habits contribute to obesity, oxidative stress, and increased cancer risk. Similar findings were reported by (Olanrewaju et. al., 2016 and WCRFI, 2018), linking dietary transition and sedentary lifestyle to higher prostate cancer burden.

Some respondents also described using water to ease their symptoms. Most of them 69.9% felt better after taking cold water, while nearly half (49.3%) said warm water helped. This doesn't point to any medical benefit, but shows how patients lean on simple, everyday strategies to manage discomfort when it comes.

Conclusion and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusion

Dietary habits, lifestyle factors, and Low screening uptake significantly influence prostate cancer outcomes in Ondo city. The study underscores the role of modifiable risk factors, particularly poor dietary practices, alcohol use, and inactivity, in shaping disease burden.

4.2 Recommendation

Public health intervention should prioritize culturally appropriate dietary education, emphasizing increased consumption of fruits, vegetables, legumes and fish, while reducing red meat, processed foods and alcohol. Prostate cancer screening should be expanded and coupled with nutrition counselling. Promotion of physical activity through community-based programs is essential. Finally, Policy makers should integrate prostate health awareness into primary healthcare services to strengthen prevention and early detection strategies.

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